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MECHANISM OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF BUSINESS ENTITIES IN THE SYSTEM OF INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC RELATIONS

МЕХАНІЗМ СТАЛОГО РОЗВИТКУ СУБ'ЄКТІВ ПІДПРИЄМНИЦТВА У СИСТЕМІ МІЖНАРОДНИХ ЕКОНОМІЧНИХ ВІДНОСИН

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Левкіна Р.В., Котко Я.М., Кулініч О.А. Механізм сталого розвитку суб'єктів підприємництва у системі міжнародних економічних відносин. Науково-методична стаття.

Метою статті є обґрунтування комплексного підходу та розробці механізму сталого розвитку суб'єктів підприємництва у системі міжнародних економічних відносин, що базується на використанні практичного досвіду запровадження концепції сталого розвитку у діяльність бізнес-структур і стратегію розвитку національної економіки країн світу для вирішення проблем економічного, екологічного і соціального характеру. У результаті наукового дослідження щодо розробки механізму для його реалізації у сучасних умовах автори дійшли до висновку про доцільність його побудови на основі існуючої системи міжнародних економічних відносин. Через міжнародні організації, що займаються вирішенням проблем соціально-економічного і екологічного характеру вони сприяють контролю над рівнем шкідливих речовин у природному середовищі, забезпечують зростаючий дохід і покращення умов життєдіяльності населення у найбільш вразливих країнах, створюють основи для прогресивних змін у ресурсо- і енергозбереженні, освіті, науці для свідомого використання природних багатств і свідомого споживання товарів.

Ключові слова: суб'єкти підприємництва, міжнародні економічні відносини, концепція сталого розвитку, соціально-економічні проблеми, зовнішньоекономічна діяльність, інтеграція

Levkina R.V., Kotko Y.M., Kulinich O.A. Mechanism of Sustainable Development of Business Entities in the System of International Economic Relations. Scientific and methodical article.

The purpose of the article is to substantiate an integrated approach and to develop a mechanism for sustainable development of business entities in the system of international economic relations based on the practical experience of implementing the concept of sustainable development in the activities of business structures and the strategy of development of the national economy of countries of the world to address economic, environmental and social issues. As a result of the scientific research on the development of a mechanism for its implementation in modern conditions, the authors conclude that it is expedient to build it on the basis of the existing system of international economic relations. Through international organizations dealing with socio-economic and environmental issues, they contribute to controlling the level of harmful substances in the environment, ensure growing incomes and improving living conditions in the poorest countries, and create the basis for progressive changes in resource and energy conservation, education, and science for the conscious use of natural resources and conscious consumption of goods.

Keywords: business entities, international economic relations, concept of sustainable development, socio-economic problems, foreign economic activity, integration

In today's globalized world economy and international economic relations, production relations between countries and their mutual dependence have become irreversible. No country can effectively address socio-economic problems without coordinating its national policy with the policies of other countries. International economic relations have acquired a new essence and new forms under the influence of trends in the global economy and scientific and technological progress. This is accompanied by a transformation of the way of thinking adequate to the realities of economic and political processes, which for Ukraine means success and recognition in the global commodity market, integration into the world economy and development of promising forms of foreign economic cooperation for business entities. The lack of long-term practical experience of Ukraine in the system of international economic relations complicates the already crisis situation

in the country, in relations with its strategic partners and in the functioning of business entities. For the latter, among the factors of competitiveness in the domestic and global markets, the implementation of a sustainable development strategy is of particular relevance, the practical implementation of which is the transition to the production of environmentally friendly and organic food products, environmental protection, cultivation of traditional crops for the area and provision of consumers with food products with a high content of natural nutrients. Thus, the development and practical implementation of a mechanism for sustainable development of business entities in the system of international economic relations, considering the adaptive experience of integrating foreign companies into world markets, is becoming increasingly important. Thus, the problem of developing Ukraine's international integration ties can be solved, and forms of interaction between its subjects and international corporations, organizations and non-legal associations can be established. The expected result of the introduction of such a mechanism is to intensify the processes of internationalization and development of the domestic economic sector.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

The study of trends in the development of international economic relations is devoted to the works of prominent research economists, including: N.V. Antipenko [1], D.M. Vasylykivsky, N.V. Pochernina, O.Y. Sohatsky [2], N.G. Georgiadi and others. Thus, in the scientific work of N. G. Georgiadi, the main characteristics of economic development are defined, which are general strategic guidelines or vectors of development and which form the basis of strategic and current plans for the economic development of enterprises in the context of accelerating international economic relations [3]. The study by V. V. Latysheva and V. O. Babina analyzes the current state of Ukraine's cooperation with international economic organizations in the context of war in order to determine the directions and prospects for further cooperation [4].

Traditionally, the development of international economic relations is characterized by multi-vector processes, which are manifested through the participation of countries in international economic integration processes as full or prospective members of integration associations. This leads to the convergence of national economies, their intersection and mutual adaptation. Gradually, the internationalization of industrial and economic relations, joint solution of economic and social problems will lead to a clear definition of the country's place at the global level and further defense of its own interests.

At the current stage of development of international economic relations, special attention should be paid to the consideration and adherence to the concept of sustainable development, as this is how the economic, environmental and social interests of countries are harmonized. The implementation of the basic principles of sustainable development in most countries is supported by active cooperation for the sake of stability in the economic, social, political, and environmental spheres. Therefore, we will use the provisions of the sustainable development concept in building a mechanism for the development of international economic relations.

The problem of developing international relations in accordance with different conditions of functioning is paid attention to by such scholars as: S.I. Arkhieriev [5], I.V. Burakovsky, G.S. Grigoriev [6], O.M. Melnyk, O.B. Naumov, V.I. Pokotylova, S.V. Fomishyn, and others. They focus on theoretical and methodological aspects as the basis for the transition of relations to the practical plane, which will implement international economic cooperation, which is a single organism - the system of international economic relations. According to G. S. Grigoriev, international economic relations should be considered on the basis of theoretical issues related to the formation of aggregate world supply and demand for goods (services), factors of production in international circulation, and the practical application of the methodology for analyzing the compliance of the national economy with the indicators of its openness and integration [6]. The work of A. I. Boyarchuk analyzes the forms of international economic relations as a set of international trade, international movement of production factors, international monetary, financial and credit relations, integration processes, international technology transfer and international business [7]. It should be noted that this approach is traditional, even classical, so we cannot but agree with this approach of the authors.

The scientific works of such researchers as: O.G. Shpikulyak, V.O. Ivanchenko [8], L.V. Shaulska, P.G. Pererva, T.O. Koieleva [9], O.I. Protosvitska [10], T.I. Demianenko [11], and others. We also have scientific experience in researching the issues of sustainable development of agricultural business entities in the context of building a strategic management mechanism [12], which requires a long period of training of highly qualified personnel [13].

Unsolved aspects of the problem

The results of our previous studies and published works provide a basis for developing a mechanism for the effective functioning of business entities and the development of international economic relations with the gradual integration of closed and semi-closed national economies that have the greatest potential for spreading the concept of sustainable development. As is well known, the concept of sustainable development means harmonization of economic, environmental and social interests, and at the macro level - the interests of the countries of the world in the process of their civilizational development [14, 15]. We have studied the principles of sustainable development and their implementation at the macro level, as well as at the level of individual regions and industries, and published them in [13]. We tested the results of studies of trends and features of Ukraine's integration into the system of international economic relations in the context of globalization processes

in publications [13-15]. It is the globalization of the economy and its impact on all countries, without exception, that contributed to the improvement of the economic and political situation in Ukraine, allowed to increase investment, and solve economic and social problems. It is thanks to active international support for Ukraine that the principles of peace and security, the rule of law in the economy and social sphere are gradually being implemented; foreign economic activity of business structures is developing; and environmental problems are being addressed.

At the same time, despite the wide range of scientific research on these issues, the issues of sustainable development of business entities in the system of international economic relations: issues of methodology and practice remain unaddressed. Most of the works focus on the conceptual and categorical apparatus of the theory of international economic relations and sustainable development, their forms, types, and principles of implementation. The presented theoretical and methodological approaches do not fully reveal the functional features of international economic relations and the functioning of business entities on the basis of sustainable development. It is necessary to develop a modern toolkit for their assessment and analysis, adapted to the current conditions of uncertainty and risk. Thus, the development of a mechanism for sustainable development of business entities, their effective integration into the system of international economic relations and growth of competitiveness is of high relevance.

The aim of the article is to substantiate an integrated approach and develop a mechanism for sustainable development of business entities in the system of international economic relations, based on the use of practical experience of introducing the concept of sustainable development into the activities of business structures to address economic, environmental and social issues.

The main part

During the years of independence, Ukraine has demonstrated a dynamic development of relations with all countries of the world, international organizations and institutions. This continues to happen on the basis of the introduction of a new economic and social order, the growth of openness of the national economy and integration [1-3].

According to A.I. Boyarchuk, international economic relations are a multi-level system of economic, trade and economic relations between countries, their international business structures, and individual legal entities and individuals [7]. In the publication of S. I. Arkhieriev defines the concept of «international economic relations» as a system of economic relations concerning the production, distribution, exchange and consumption of products that have gone beyond national borders [5].

We agree with this option, but the need to generalize approaches to the definition of «international economic relations» remains. Thus, international economic relations are a set of relations that arise between entities from different countries in the process of division of labor in trade, economic cooperation, exchange and consumption of goods (services) and capital under conditions of limited resources and within the world economy as an integrated system.

According to another approach, the structure of the system of international economic relations is made up of socio-economic, political, scientific, cultural, organizational, environmental and other relations. International economic relations as a system of various economic ties of national economies, which are realized through the international division of labor and consist of a set of international trade in goods and services; international capital flows; international migration relations; international monetary and financial relations; international integration (Fig. 1) [6-7].

The international division of labor arises under the influence of factors that become active in the environment in a certain period of time and is largely provoked by the development of scientific and technological progress, innovations and the gradual transition of national economies and the world economy to a new technological system. As an international specialization of countries, their participation in international cooperative production relations, the international division of labor is a prerequisite for the emergence and development of a system of international economic relations that is resistant to negative trends.

Among the groups of factors of influence (natural and geographical, socio-economic, scientific and technical) in different periods of civilization development, the most influential ones are distinguished. If during the millennia of natural exchange and provision of basic needs of mankind, natural and geographical factors were decisive, because it was climatic and natural conditions, population size that ensured food production, then in the middle ages, people's skills, education, population density, ability to use not only simple tools, but also complex mechanisms for cultivating land, producing industrial goods, ability to use monetary units and simple financial transactions came to the fore.

At the latter stages, the most popular are scientific and technical factors that determine the country's potential to use innovative solutions in production, trade, management and business organization. Such innovations include digital technologies, biological and genetic technologies, information and communication technologies, and nanotechnologies. The latter are so rapidly and widely used in modern business that they require a logical continuation as the introduction of information protection technologies (trade secret protection, cybersecurity technologies, project management) [16]. Such technologies are used to protect the interests of national producers, individual projects, and the country's economic security [17].

Figure 1. Benefits of Ukraine's integration into the system of international economic relations in terms of its individual forms on the basis of sustainable development

Source: compiled by authors on materials [6, 7]

The practical result of innovations at the macro level was the acceleration of economic reforms, harmonization of economic legislation in accordance with the signed agreements within the GATT and GATS, and the effectiveness of the WTO. The growth of foreign investment and investor confidence, the introduction of reasonable norms and effective rules are a condition for the most favored nation treatment in the markets of trading partner countries; ensuring Ukraine's gradual integration into leading integration associations (e.g., the European Union) with the obligatory protection of the national interests of Ukraine and its business entities [18-20].

International trade occupies a leading place in the system of international economic relations, which is determined by the process of realization of the results of world economic relations (capital transfer, production cooperation, cooperation, etc.) and determines the dynamics of international exchange of services, monetary, financial and credit relations, as well as the growth and deepening of interregional and interstate relations, which are an important prerequisite for the international division of labor and internationalization of relations [3-4].

International labor migration is becoming increasingly global. Currently, it has intensified in the vast majority of countries.

According to statistics, as of the end of January 2024, 4.9 million Ukrainians are abroad seeking protection from the war. As of January 2024, the largest share of Ukrainian refugees in Europe was in Germany (30%) and Poland (22%). Outside of the European Union, the number of Ukrainians accepted since the beginning of the full-scale invasion is the largest in the United States (280 thousand people), the United Kingdom (253.2 thousand people) and Canada (210.2 thousand people) [6, 21]. International labor migration means the process of spontaneous or organized movement of the working-age population, which is determined by the nature of the national or international division of labor, the level of development of productive forces and industrial relations, and the operation of economic laws. The main socio-economic factors that determine the modern migration of

domestic labor force are the lack of security in their own country, lack of housing, poor economic and sanitary living conditions, and unemployment.

International economic integration is a direct manifestation of the internationalization of economic life, has a universal character of international relations that create the basis for the approximation of national economies, their intersection in the economic sense and mutual adaptation. In practical terms, it is accompanied by mutual adaptation of industries of different countries, border areas, international business entities, and the formation of international economic complexes [7]. International integration in the form of mutual adaptation and joint development develops in those countries that have common borders and close economic ties based on geographical proximity, common traditions and customs [5].

International economic relations are the relations between different levels of the world economy regarding the implementation of the system of international economic relations: trade, financial, scientific and technical, social, information, etc. The main participants of international economic relations are their subjects engaged in foreign economic activity. The main subjects of international economic relations include: state institutions; regional associations, private business structures, international corporations, and international organizations. Accordingly, the objects of international economic relations include: goods (services); factors of production (entrepreneurial abilities, labor resources, capital, land resources, information), multilateral cooperation (overcoming the backwardness of economic development, rational use of natural resources, development of human potential) [6, 7, 12-15]. Therefore, the external environment for an entrepreneurial entity is a set of components of the system of international economic relations and the national system.

The main objectives of Ukraine's economic policy are to ensure dynamic socio-economic growth through the introduction of scientific and technological factors and the efficient use of production factors. In addition, the tasks include maintaining macroeconomic balance; conducting social and economic reforms (aimed at restructuring the institutional system, balancing the economy, social sphere and environment); diversifying integration processes, and expanding into the markets of underdeveloped countries. At the same time, considering the state of integration of the national economy of Ukraine into the world economy allows us to detail the profile of international specialization, identify promising areas of international cooperation with countries that have the greatest potential and determine the directions of changes in the structure of the national economy. This provokes problems that need to be addressed immediately and intensifies competition in the domestic and global markets for goods (services); emigration of labor force for permanent residence. In such changing conditions and uncertainty, business entities operate on the basis of sustainable development. Fig. 2 schematically presents measures to minimize and prevent the manifestation of negative integration and globalization processes on the economy of Ukraine on the basis of sustainable development [6, 7, 21, 22].

Figure 2. Opportunities for Ukraine to minimize and prevent the manifestation of problems of international economic relations in the context of implementing the concept of sustainable development

Source: compiled by authors on materials [6, 7, 11, 14, 15]

By implementing the principles of sustainable development at all levels of the international economic relations system, in political and managerial decision-making processes, the cooperation is based on the principles of combining the efforts of government authorities from different countries, civil society, business entities and international business, scientific, educational and public organizations. The cooperation is preceded by a deep and comprehensive analysis of social, economic and social problems. Various methods of evaluation and analysis are usually used, among which the most acceptable is the method of integrated indicators. The concept of sustainable development plays a key role in harmonizing the policies of different countries regarding the directions of development of international economic relations and, thus, the effectiveness of their practical implementation increases and the efficiency of business entities increases [7, 11, 13, 16].

Figure 3. The mechanism of sustainable development of business entities in the system of international economic relations

Source: authors' own elaboration

Fig. 3 shows the mechanism of sustainable development of business entities in the system of international economic relations. The basis of such a mechanism is a set of business entities and subjects of international economic relations that operate on the basis of sustainable development, are related to the production of organic agri-food products, use them as raw materials for further processing into materials for sewing clothes, shoes, and household goods. Such enterprises are engaged in the recycling and further processing of previously used items, promote sustainable development goals, and provide expert assistance and advice to those interested in maintaining the ecological state of the environment and preserving biodiversity.

Thus, they influence the objects of international economic relations and each other. Implementation of the principles of freedom of IEA subjects and freedom to choose the type of activity and non-discrimination is ensured by the following functions of the IEA system: organizational, regulatory, controlling, stimulating, resource-saving. Thus, through the creation of international organizations that deal with the problems of socio-economic and environmental development; control the level of chemical emissions into the environment, research and try to regulate the level of income and living conditions of the population in the poorest countries, progressive changes are taking place in the direction of resource and energy conservation, conscious use of natural resources and conscious consumption of goods. The experience and methodological developments of the scientific and educational community on the way to educating and shaping the ecological paradigm of the younger generation are useful [13].

After all, Ukraine needs a new paradigm of the national strategy for economic modernization based on adequate principles, allowing it to form the basis for competitiveness in the context of globalization. The modernization of our country's development strategy should be based on the latest doctrine of sustainable development in the development of international economic relations, as it is necessary to focus on an efficient industrial and technological system with a socially and environmentally balanced post-industrial society, which the world's leading countries are already striving for. Accordingly, in our opinion, it is necessary to create a mechanism for the effective organization and functioning of the IEA, considering sustainable development, which will improve the process of establishing closer relations with various actors in international economic relations (Fig. 3). The peculiarity of the mechanism of sustainable development of business entities in the system of international economic relations is the implementation of principles and methods aimed at increasing and improving the country's international trade, including in environmentally friendly and organic food products, as well as goods that support this production. It is also necessary to increase investments, financial transfers and other forms of financial interaction between countries [7, 11, 18, 19, 22, 24].

The main directions for further development of this mechanism are: growth of integration processes in the form of regional economic unions, expansion of the common market for goods/services, capital and labor; trade liberalization, which is aimed at removing or reducing tariff and non-tariff barriers between countries, which contributes to increased trade, investment and economic growth at the global level, as the removal of trade barriers can increase economic integration between countries, increase the volume of mutual trade and create new jobs; improvement of investment flows, which reflect the global movement of capital between countries, contributing to economic growth, infrastructure development and job creation (modernization of infrastructure, energy and mining; programs and projects in the field of energy, transport and environmental protection; development of digital technologies (digital platforms, e-commerce, blockchain technologies) contribute to the creation of global markets; technological exchange and cooperation are activators of innovation, productivity growth, and economic and social development at the global level; establishing close cooperation with international organizations (WB, IMF, EBRD, regional banks) provides the necessary financial resources, advisory services and assistance in implementing reforms aimed at increasing economic stability, minimizing social problems, as their activities contribute to the creation of a favorable socio-economic and environmental environment for international trade; formation of environmental cooperation, which is important for preserving the environment and ensuring sustainable development of economies, maintaining public health, reducing poverty and promoting peace and security; implementation of international standards and norms that ensure a unified approach to production, trade and services, thus contributing to the growth and efficiency of international economic interaction [6, 7, 24-26].

Conclusions

Thus, in this scientific publication, we have substantiated the theoretical and methodological foundations for the formation and functioning of the mechanism of sustainable development of business entities in the system of international economic relations. The introduction of the concept of sustainable development and penetration of its principles into the sphere of international economic relations facilitates the adoption of appropriate decisions in the field of public policy and the real productive sector of the economy using the recommendations of governments, decisions of civil society, efficiency of business entities, and research results of scientific organizations and non-governmental institutions. After all, their cooperation is based on a thorough and comprehensive analysis of social, economic and social problems using an integrated method. Thus, the concept of sustainable development plays a key role in harmonizing the policy of international economic relations and, accordingly, affects their development and the development of national business entities.

The essence of the mechanism of sustainable development of business entities in the system of international economic relations is to build the capacity of business entities to implement the principles and methods aimed at increasing the volume and expansion of world trade flows, growth of investments, financial transfers and other forms of economic interaction between countries.

Abstract

The purpose of the article is to substantiate an integrated approach and to develop a mechanism for sustainable development of business entities in the system of international economic relations based on the practical experience of implementing the concept of sustainable development in the activities of business structures and the strategy of development of the national economy of countries of the world to address economic, environmental and social issues. To achieve this goal, the following tasks have been set, in particular: to determine the main characteristics of economic development of the world economy and national economies in the system of international economic relations; to analyze the current state and trends of Ukraine's cooperation with international economic organizations in the current conditions of war, to identify problems and directions for minimizing and preventing the manifestation of problems of international economic relations for the national economy of Ukraine in the context of the implementation of the concept of sustainable development and prospects for further cooperation; determining the relationship between the system of international economic relations and the concept of sustainable development for business entities, which is implemented through the mechanism of their sustainable development in the system of international economic relations proposed by us. As a result of the scientific research on the development of a mechanism for its implementation in modern conditions, the authors conclude that it is expedient to build it on the basis of the existing system of international economic relations. Such a system has developed and functions under the influence of various factors which simultaneously affect the subjects of such relations, including national economies, international business entities, international organizations, integration associations, and business entities. The basis of such a mechanism is a set of business entities and subjects of international economic relations that operate on the basis of sustainable development, mainly related to the production and marketing of organic agri-food and environmentally friendly products, use them as raw materials or supply them to other enterprises, etc. They affect the objects of international economic relations, influence each other, international relations, and, among other things, determine the development trend of the world economy as a whole. Through international organizations dealing with socio-economic and environmental issues, they contribute to controlling the level of harmful substances in the environment, ensure growing incomes and improving living conditions in the poorest countries, and create the basis for progressive changes in resource and energy conservation, education, and science for the conscious use of natural resources and conscious consumption of goods.

Список літератури:

1. Антипенко Н., Почерніна, Н., Васильківський, Д. (2024). Глобалізація та її вплив на міжнародні економічні відносини. Економіка та суспільство. № 59. DOI: 10.32782/2524-0072/2024-59-2.
2. Сохацький О. (2024). Поліпарадигмальна невизначеність міжнародних економічних відносин у системі глобальної безпеки. Вісник економіки. № 1, С. 198-217. DOI: 10.35774/visnyk2024.01.198.
3. Георгіаді Н.Г. (2022). Розвиток підприємств в умовах активізування міжнародних економічних відносин. Проблеми сучасних трансформацій. Серія: економіка та управління. 5. DOI: 10.54929/2786-5738-2022-5-04-05.
4. Латишева В.В., Бабіна В.О. (2023). Співробітництво України з міжнародними організаціями в умовах війни: проблеми, напрями та перспективи. Філософія та політологія в контексті сучасної культури. Т. 15. № 1. С. 149-157.
5. Архієреєв С.І., Волоснікова Н.М., Климова С.О. (2019). Міжнародна економіка і міжнародні економічні відносини: навч. посібн. Харків: НТУ «ХПІ». 234 с.
6. Григор'єв Г.С. Міжнародна економіка: практ. Київ: НаУКМА, 2024. 145 с.
7. Боярчук А.І., Огородник Р.П., Плющик І.А., Антофій Н.М., Федорова Н.С. (2018). Міжнародні економічні відносини: навч. посібн. Херсон: ТОВ «ВКФ «СТАР» ЛТД». 374 с.
8. Шпикуляк О.Г., Іванченко В.О. (2020). Формування індексів та індикаторів сталого розвитку підприємництва в сільському господарстві: теоретико-методичні підходи. Економіка АПК. № 9. С. 114-122.
9. Шаульська Л.В, Перерва П.Г., Коєлева Т.О. (2023). Дослідження впливу підприємницьких ризиків на сталий розвиток підприємства. Енергозбереження, енергетика, енергоаудит. № 3 (181). С. 14-23.
10. Протосвіцька, О. І. (2021). Забезпечення конкурентоспроможності аграрних підприємств в умовах сталого розвитку: автореф. дис. канд. екон. наук: спец. 08.00.04 «Економіка та

- управління підприємствами (за видами економічної діяльності)»: захищена 16.03.21 / Протосвіцька Оксана Іванівна; наук. кер. О.М. Федорчук; Одес. нац. акад. харч. технологій, [Міжнар. ун-т бізнесу і права]. Одеса: ОНАХТ. 22 с.
11. Дем'яненко Т.І. (2020). Сталий розвиток вітчизняних підприємств в сучасних економічних умовах. Вчені записки ТНУ імені В.І. Вернадського. Т. 31 (70). № 2. DOI: 10.32838/2523-4803/70-2-30.
 12. Левкіна Р.В. (2013). Стратегічне управління виробничою діяльністю підприємств овочівництва: теорія, методологія, практика: монографія. Херсон: «Гринь». 324 с.
 13. Левкіна Р.В., Левкін А.В. (2021). Освіта для забезпечення сталого розвитку суб'єктів аграрного підприємництва. Університетська наука і освіта: традиції та інновації: Міжнародна науково-методична конференція. Харків: Харківський національний технічний університет сільського господарства ім. Петра Василенка. С. 22-24.
 14. Fedicheva, K., Kochetkov, O., Honcharenko, S., Levkina, R., Bichevin M. (2021). Controlling, monitoring and diagnostics in identifying effective management practices of agricultural enterprises. *Agricultural and Resource Economics*. Vo. 7. Issue. 2. Pp. 200-218. DOI: 10.22004/ag.econ.313636.
 15. Levkina, R.V. (2013). The formation of organizational-economic mechanism for stable development of agricultural enterprises. *Technology Audit and Production Reserves*. 5(3(13)). P. 16-18. DOI: 10.15587/2312-8372.2013.18518.
 16. Kavun, S., Levkina, R., Kotko, Ya., Levkin, D., Levkin, A. (2023). Information Security in Project Management for the Financial and Budgetary Capacity of the National Economy. CPITS-2023-II: Cybersecurity Providing in Information and Telecommunication Systems. CEUR Workshop Proceedings. Vol. 3550. Pp. 246-254. [Електронний ресурс]. – Режим доступу: <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3550/short8.pdf>.
 17. Levkin, A., Levkina, R., Petrenko, A., Chaliy, I. (2019). Economic Security as a Result of Modern Biotechnology Implementation: 2019 IEEE International Scientific-Practical Conference Problems of Infocommunications Science and Technology (PIC S&T'2019) (8-11 October 2019 Kyiv). Kyiv. P. 139-142.
 18. Latysheva, V., Babina, V. (2023). Співробітництво України з міжнародними організаціями в умовах війни: проблеми, напрями та перспективи. *Філософія та політологія в контексті сучасної культури*, 15 (1). С. 149-157. DOI: 10.15421/352317.
 19. Левкіна Р.В., Котко Я.М. (2022). Міжнародний досвід фінансово-правового регулювання діяльності фондового ринку. І Міжнародна науково-практична конференція «Фінансові інструменти сталого розвитку держави в умовах системної економічної трансформації». Хмельницький: Херсонський національний технічний університет.
 20. Levkina, R.V., Levkin, A.V., Kotko, Ya.M. (2022). Risk management system in transnational corporations. Міжнародна науково-практична конференція «Міжнародні економічні відносини: сталий розвиток України в умовах глобалізації та європейської економічної інтеграції: проблеми, перспективи, ефективність. Фенікс-2022». Харків: НТУ «ХПІ».
 21. Батракова Т., Фоменко С. (2023). Сучасний стан зовнішньої торгівлі України в умовах економічної нестабільності. *Цифрова економіка та економічна безпека*, (4 (04), 56-62. DOI: 10.32782/dees.4-10.
 22. Левкіна Р.В., Левкін А.В. Міжнародний трансфер технологій як чинник розвитку агропромислового виробництва. *Вісник Харківського національного технічного університету сільського господарства*. № 161. Харків: ХНТУСГ. 2015. С. 31-37. [Електронний ресурс]. – Режим доступу: <https://repo.btu.kharkov.ua/handle/123456789/26394>.
 23. Микитин О., Завербний С. (2023). Особливості становлення і гармонійного розвитку партнерських взаємовідносин за євроінтеграційних умов. *Економіка та суспільство*, (57). DOI: 10.32782/2524-0072/2023-57-38.
 24. Levkina, R.V., Kotko, Ya.M., Levkin, A.V. (2022). Sustainable development of unions of territorial societies: international experience. *Sustainable Development: Modern Theories and Best Practices: Materials of the Monthly International Scientific and Practical Conference*. Tallinn: Teadmus OÜ.
 25. Капінос Г., Ларіонова К. (2023). Проблеми управління сталим розвитком України в умовах війни. *Modeling the development of the economic systems*. (1), С. 93-103. DOI: 10.31891/mdes/2023-7-13.
 26. Дубина М., Сердюк Д. (2023). Забезпечення сталого розвитку України в умовах невизначеності та турбулентності зовнішнього середовища. Проблеми і перспективи економіки та управління. № 4 (36), С. 9-25. DOI: 10.25140/2411-5215-2023-4(36)-9-25.

References:

1. Antipenko, N., Pochernina, N., & Vasylykivskiy, D. (2024). Globalization and its impact on international economic relations. *Economy and Society*, 59. DOI: 10.32782/2524-0072/2024-59-2 [in Ukrainian].
2. Sokhatskyi, O. (2024). Polyparadigmatic uncertainty of international economic relations in the global security system. *Herald of Economics*, 1, 198-217. DOI: 10.35774/visnyk2024.01.198 [in Ukrainian].
3. Heorhiadi, N.H. (2022). Enterprise development in conditions of intensifying international economic relations. *Problems of Modern Transformations: Economics and Management Series*, 5. DOI: 10.54929/2786-5738-2022-5-04-05 [in Ukrainian].
4. Latysheva, V.V., & Babina, V.O. (2023). Ukraine's cooperation with international organizations during wartime: Problems, directions and prospects. *Philosophy and Political Science in the Context of Modern Culture*, 15(1), 149-157 [in Ukrainian].
5. Arkhiereiev, S.I., Volosnikova, N.M., & Klymova, S.O. (2019). International economics and international economic relations. NTU "KhPI" [in Ukrainian].
6. Hryhoriev, H.S. (2024). International economics: Practice. NaUKMA [in Ukrainian].
7. Boiarchuk, A.I., Ohorodnyk, R.P., Pliushchik, I.A., Antofii, N.M., & Fedorova, N.Y. (2018). International economic relations. VKF "STAR" LTD [in Ukrainian].
8. Shpykuliak, O.H., & Ivanchenko, V.O. (2020). Formation of indices and indicators of sustainable development of entrepreneurship in agriculture: Theoretical and methodological approaches. *Economy of AIC*, 9, 114-122 [in Ukrainian].
9. Shaulska, L.V., Pererva, P.H., & Koelielieva, T.O. (2023). Research on the impact of entrepreneurial risks on sustainable enterprise development. *Energy Saving, Energy, Energy Audit*, 3(181), 14-23 [in Ukrainian].
10. Protosivitska, O.I. (2021). Ensuring the competitiveness of agricultural enterprises in conditions of sustainable development [Doctoral dissertation, Odesa National Academy of Food Technologies] [in Ukrainian].
11. Demianenko, T.I. (2020). Sustainable development of domestic enterprises in modern economic conditions. *Scientific Notes of TNU Vernadsky*, 31(70)(2). DOI: 10.32838/2523-4803/70-2-30 [in Ukrainian].
12. Levkina, R.V. (2013). Strategic management of production activities of vegetable enterprises: Theory, methodology, practice. Hryn [in Ukrainian].
13. Levkina, R.V., & Levkin, A.V. (2021). Education for sustainable development of agricultural entrepreneurship entities. In *University Science and Education: Traditions and Innovations* (pp. 22-24). Kharkiv National Technical University of Agriculture [in Ukrainian].
14. Fedicheva, K., Kochetkov, O., Honcharenko, S., Levkina, R., & Bichevin, M. (2021). Controlling, monitoring and diagnostics in identifying effective management practices of agricultural enterprises. *Agricultural and Resource Economics*, 7(2), 200-218. DOI: 10.22004/ag.econ.313636 [in English].
15. Levkina, R.V. (2013). The formation of organizational-economic mechanism for stable development of agricultural enterprises. *Technology Audit and Production Reserves*, 5(3), 16-18. DOI: 10.15587/2312-8372.2013.18518 [in English].
16. Kavun, S., Levkina, R., Kotko, Y., Levkin, D., & Levkin, A. (2023). Information security in project management for the financial and budgetary capacity of the national economy. In *CPITS-2023-II: Cybersecurity Providing in Information and Telecommunication Systems* (pp. 246-254). CEUR Workshop Proceedings [in English].
17. Levkin, A., Levkina, R., Petrenko, A., & Chaliy, I. (2019). Economic security as a result of modern biotechnology implementation. In *2019 IEEE International Scientific-Practical Conference Problems of Infocommunications Science and Technology (PIC S&T'2019)* (pp. 139-142) [in English].
18. Latysheva, V., & Babina, V. (2023). Ukraine's cooperation with international organizations during wartime: Problems, directions and prospects. *Philosophy and Political Science in the Context of Modern Culture*, 15(1), 149-157. DOI: 10.15421/352317 [in Ukrainian].
19. Levkina, R.V., & Kotko, Y.M. (2022). International experience of financial and legal regulation of stock market activities. In *First International Scientific and Practical Conference "Financial Instruments of Sustainable State Development in Conditions of Systemic Economic Transformation."* Kherson National Technical University [in Ukrainian].
20. Levkina, R.V., Levkin, A.V., & Kotko, Y.M. (2022). Risk management system in transnational corporations. In *International Scientific and Practical Conference "International Economic Relations: Sustainable Development of Ukraine in the Context of Globalization and European Economic Integration: Problems, Prospects, Efficiency. Phoenix-2022."* National Technical University "Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute." [in English].

21. Batrakova, T., & Fomenko, S. (2023). Current state of Ukraine's foreign trade under economic instability. *Digital Economy and Economic Security*, 4(04), 56-62. DOI: 10.32782/dees.4-10 [in Ukrainian].
22. Levkina, R.V., & Levkin, A.V. (2015). International technology transfer as a factor in the development of agro-industrial production. *Bulletin of Kharkiv National Technical University of Agriculture*, 161, 31-37. Retrieved from: <https://repo.btu.kharkov.ua/handle/123456789/26394> [in Ukrainian].
23. Mykytyn, O., & Zaverbnyi, S. (2023). Features of formation and harmonious development of partnership relations under European integration conditions. *Economy and Society*, (57). DOI: 10.32782/2524-0072/2023-57-38 [in Ukrainian].
24. Levkina, R.V., Kotko, Y.M., & Levkin, A.V. (2022). Sustainable development of unions of territorial societies: International experience. In *Sustainable Development: Modern Theories and Best Practices: Materials of the Monthly International Scientific and Practical Conference*. Teadmus OÜ [in English].
25. Kapinos, H., & Larionova, K. (2023). Problems of managing sustainable development of Ukraine during wartime. *Modeling the Development of the Economic Systems*, (1), 93-103. DOI: 10.31891/mdes/2023-7-13 [in Ukrainian].
26. Dubyna, M., & Serdiuk, D. (2023). Ensuring sustainable development of Ukraine under conditions of uncertainty and environmental turbulence. *Problems and Prospects of Economics and Management*, 4(36), 9-25. DOI: 10.25140/2411-5215-2023-4(36)-9-25 [in Ukrainian].

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